

THETIDA

PRESERVING UNDERWATER
AND COASTAL HERITAGE

GUIDELINES TO IDENTIFY AND REPORT ON COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

The THETIDA project foresees extensive communication and dissemination of the project objectives, activities, methodology and outputs.

IDENTIFICATION OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND OUTREACH OPPORTUNITIES

Communication, dissemination and outreach opportunities include **THETIDA-labelled events** and the **presentation of THETIDA** at workshops, conferences and other events, public speeches, publication of articles in printed and online media or websites, dissemination on TV, YouTube channels, etc.

THETIDA-labelled events

A THETIDA labelled event is any sort of event including workshops, conferences, side events and online webinars i) organised by any project's partner for the execution of any project activity; ii) open to external partners; iii) funded with project budget.

To inform us of the THETIDA events you are planning to organise, a table is available on SharePoint: [THETIDA foreseen events.xlsx](#)

Please, fill in this table as soon as you start planning the event and no later than 6 weeks in advance to the event's implementation.

Once the organization of the event is confirmed, please create a subfolder in the appropriate folder and name it in the following format: **DATE_EVENT_NAME_RESPONSIBLE PARTNER** and drop the material (including banners, visuals, videos or other multi-media contents related to the activity) there.

External events

External events are to be considered any kind of event organised by organisations not part of the THETIDA consortium or organised by them but for purposes not directly related with the implementation of project activities featuring the participation of one partner as contributor.

To identify communication, dissemination and outreach opportunities, a table is available on THETIDA's SharePoint: [Potential external events and other communication opportunities.xlsx](#)

Please, fill in this table as soon as you identify the opportunity and no later than 6 weeks in advance to the deadline to propose our contribution to the identified opportunity.

COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES

Effective communication from all partners is important to promote the project and its impacts and results. To avoid creating confusion on the public's mind, it is important to maintain harmonised communication throughout the different platforms all along the duration of the project.

To achieve these two goals of efficiency and coherence, partners are invited to use the [Communication Toolbox](#) available on THETIDA SharePoint when presenting the project internally or externally.

The communication toolbox includes but is not limited to:

- a) Logos (THETIDA and Partners);
- b) Posters, leaflets, banners, brochures (soon to be translated in relevant languages);
- c) Visual identity including colour palette and fonts;
- d) Templates;
- e) A general presentation of the project.

Partners are invited to use appropriate fonts, colours, and general themes when publishing or presenting anything related to the THETIDA project, either on social media or on any other platform. Templates have been created to ease the harmonisation.

In-Person events

When attending to in-person events, partners should use promotional materials as updated on the communication toolbox (leaflets, posters, etc.). Materials are to be used in accordance with the aims of the event attended by the partner. For instance, when organising a THETIDA-labelled event, partners are invited to use the official [roll-up](#) while the [brochure and flyer](#) could also be used for more informal events.

In the week following any events, partners are invited to share with WP6 leader (EURISY) some content to be used on social media (pictures, videos, a short text describing the event itself and the role played by the partner during that event, etc.).

Social Media

Partners are advised to repost/share THETIDA content on their own platforms to develop project visibility and present its advancements.

For external events or THETIDA-labelled events requiring registration/application, effective social media campaigns can help gathering attendance. Therefore, all partners are invited to share on their social platforms the mentioned events.

REPORTING ON COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

Partners are invited to report on the communication, dissemination and outreach activities for which they are responsible **within the week following the implementation of such activities**. To facilitate the reporting process, a step-by-step procedure has been developed, and is relying on the following folder: [Reporting on Communication, Dissemination and Outreach Activities](#).

If you are not able to access SharePoint, please send the required information via email to anais.guy@eurisy.eu.

Description & Purpose

Dissemination activities related to results achieved within the framework of THETIDA (*i.e.*, publications or presentations of work done within the framework of THETIDA, such as journal publications, technical articles, participation in conferences, etc.) **must be approved beforehand by the THETIDA Consortium**.

The dissemination procedure is to be followed by all partners equally, regarding every dissemination activity (including activities unrelated to results dissemination, such as participation to events, exhibitions, use of leaflets and brochures, etc. for which steps 4 to 6 do not apply) to:

- a) Produce high quality THETIDA publications and presentations;
- b) Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- c) Efficiently monitor, record and promote the dissemination activities of the project;
- d) Secure the brand identity of the project and the EC rules to be followed;

The WP6 leader (EURISY) is responsible for ensuring compliance with the procedures. **All partners are called to contribute efficiently to the dissemination of the project.**

Step by Step Procedure

Before any dissemination activity related to the THETIDA project, the initiator of the activity should:

STEP 1: Notify WP6 Leader (Anaïs Guy: anais.guy@eurisy.eu, Annalisa Donati: annalisa.donati@eurisy.eu) & THETIDA's Coordinator Team (Panos Michalis: p.michalis@iccs.gr, Irini Krimpa: irini.krimpa@iccs.gr), **at least 30 working days in advance** about the intention to participate on a dissemination activity, sharing the details of the activity (date of event, name of journal, title of activity, audience, etc.),

their specific role in it (presenter, organiser, speaker in a session, etc.)

a short description (up to 150 words) of the activity and how it is related to THETIDA (see *Table n°1: Relevant information* below);

STEP 2: Register the activity in the [Dissemination Registry](#) specifying all the details regarding the activity, as indicated in each column of the file;

STEP 3: If applicable, **store the relevant material** (abstract, draft paper, poster, article, presentation, press release etc.) in the [Reporting on Communication, Dissemination and Outreach Activities](#) on Teams, under the related sub-folder:

- a) [Articles and Publications](#): Records information about articles, publications and contributions related to THETIDA published in printed and online journals, publications and webpages.
- b) [Communication on Media](#): Records information about communication, dissemination and outreach made through printed and online media.
- c) [External Events](#): Records information about workshops, conferences, and other events to which you contributed by providing information or materials about THETIDA.
- d) [Our Events](#): Records information about workshops, training, and other THETIDA-labelled events.

Once in the sub-folder, please create a folder in the following format **DATE_ACTIVITY NAME_RESPONSIBLE PARTNER** and drop the materials there.

STEP 4: WP6 leader has 2 days to react and send the request to the Consortium for approval, modification or rejection;

STEP 5: Any Consortium member may raise a modification or rejection request along with comments which should be sent to the WP6 leader within 15 days; no response is considered as an approval;

STEP 6: The WP6 leader informs the initiator of the dissemination activity and the Project Coordinator about the decision.

In case of:

- a) **Approval:** The initiator may proceed with the submission or realization of the planned dissemination activity;
- b) **Conflict/objection:** Any Consortium member can object to the proposed dissemination activity, for example in cases of risk of disclosure of restricted or confidential information. The objection has to include a clear reasoning as well as a precise request for necessary modifications that would make the dissemination acceptable.

The issue is discussed among the Coordinator, the WP6 Leader and the involved partners.

Dissemination Activities Report

Within **ten working days after the realisation of the dissemination activity**, the partner should upload a fully filled [Dissemination Report](#) together with the dissemination material presented (*i.e.* final paper, presentation, poster etc.) on the [Dissemination Activity Inventory](#) accessible anytime by any project partner. It is recommended that the lead partner of every dissemination activity provides the WP6 Leader with pictures/videos of the participation at the event. The partners are requested to complete all the fields briefly and clearly, trying to avoid the use of abbreviations.

EU Acknowledgement

Since 2021, all recipients of EU funds have the legal obligation to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received EU funding. This requirement ensures visibility and transparency. For projects funded under Horizon Europe, this requirement is specified under Article 17 of the Grant Agreement. The obligation requires all beneficiaries, managing authorities and implementing partners of EU funding to acknowledge the support from the European Union on all communication materials. An important element with this regard is the European Union emblem and the funding statement which must be displayed prominently¹ on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels and other communication products:

Horizontal:

**Funded by
the European Union**

Vertical:

**Funded by
the European Union**

For any communication activity, presentation, on-line material, hard copy/printed material, the EU emblem must be displayed, along with the phrase:

“THETIDA project is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

For any infrastructure & equipment, the EU emblem must be displayed, along with the phrase:

“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of the THETIDA project, which is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

For any (scientific) publication/technical paper, the acknowledgement must be displayed as follows:

“This research has been conducted as part of the THETIDA project, which is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Useful Links

Dissemination Folder	SharePoint Access
Dissemination Activities Registry	SharePoint Access
Dissemination Report	SharePoint Access
Dissemination Activity Inventory	SharePoint Access

Table n°1: Relevant information

TITLE OF ACTIVITY	

Description / Short Summary

Relation to
THETIDA